

Operations with n-Refined Literal Neutrosophic Numbers using the Identification Method and the n-Refined AH-Isometry

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Abstract

If we know the determinate and sub-indeterminate part(s) of an argument $a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 + \dots + a_nI_n$ how do we similarly find the determinate and sub-indeterminate part(s) of a function (or operation) of this argument $f(a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 + \dots + a_nI_n)$? The AH-Isometry is designed to do just that.

The function f may be of one or more variables (arguments), it may also be some unary or n-ary operation. Real examples are presented in this paper of such arguments and functions.

We now present for the first time the most general form, the n-Refined AH-Isometry.

Keywords: Indeterminacy, Sub-Indeterminacies, n-Refined Literal and Numerical Neutrosophic Numbers, Identification Method, AH-Isometry, n-Refined Neutrosophic AH-Isometry

1. Introduction

The literal indeterminacy (I) was for the first time refined/split into literal sub-indeterminacies (I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n) by Smarandache [1] in 2015, who defined a multiplication law of these literal sub-indeterminacies to be able to build the Refined I-Neutrosophic Algebraic Structures.

The AH-Isometry [2] was firstly introduced by Mohammad Abobala and Ahmad Hatip in 2021, where AH stands for Abobala-Hatip.

The 2-Refined Neutrosophic AH-Isometry [3] was introduced by Celik and Hatip in 2022. Many papers [5-10] were published about this fundamental AH-Isometry in the rings of neutrosophic literal numbers.

We now introduce for the first time the n-Refined Neutrosophic AH-Isometry.

2. Operations with n-Refined Literal Neutrosophic Numbers

Let's have the following two n-Refined Literal Neutrosophic Numbers:

$$N_1 = a_0 + a_1 I_1 + a_2 I_2 + \dots + a_m I_m \text{ where } a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m \text{ are real or complex numbers,}$$

and similarly

$$N_2 = b_0 + b_1 I_1 + b_2 I_2 + \dots + b_m I_m \text{ where } b_0, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m \text{ are real or complex numbers,}$$

The first three are Straightforward Operations:

2.1. Addition:

$$N_1 + N_2 = (a_0 + b_0) + (a_1 + b_1)I_1 + (a_2 + b_2)I_2 + \dots + (a_m + b_m)I_m$$

2.2. Subtraction:

$$N_1 - N_2 = (a_0 - b_0) + (a_1 - b_1)I_1 + (a_2 - b_2)I_2 + \dots + (a_m - b_m)I_m$$

2.3. Scalar Multiplication:

Let c be a real or complex number. Then:

$$c \cdot N_1 = c \cdot a_0 + c \cdot a_1 I_1 + c \cdot a_2 I_2 + \dots + c \cdot a_m I_m$$

2.4. Multiplication:

In many previous applications the easiest way of multiplication (intersection) of sub-indeterminacies was defined as:

$$I_j \cdot I_k = I_{\min\{j,k\}} \text{ for all } i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}.$$

Consequently, $(I_j)^2 = (I_j)^r = I_j$, for any integer $r \geq 1$,

and

$$I_{j_1} \cdot I_{j_2} \cdot \dots \cdot I_{j_p} = I_{\min\{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_p\}}$$

also

$$\sqrt[s]{I_j} = I_j, \text{ for integer } s \geq 1, \text{ since, raising both sides to the } s\text{-power, one gets:}$$

$$(\sqrt[s]{I_j})^s = (I_j)^s = I_j.$$

2.5. Negative Exponent:

$$(I_j)^{-m}, m > 0, \text{ is undefined.}$$

2.6. Remark

The multiplication and division of the literal or numerical sub-indeterminacies ($I_a \cdot I_k$ or $I_a \div I_k$) are defined by experts depending on each specific application.

These applications on the literal sub-indeterminacies do not, in general, coincide with the same applications on the numerical sub-indeterminacies).

2.7. Division by Identification Method of 2-Refined Neutrosophic Literal Numbers:

Let's divide $N_1 \div N_2$ by the identification method.

The determinate part of the 2-refined literal neutrosophic number $N_1 = a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2$ is a_0 , while a_1 is its first sub-indeterminate part, and a_2 is its second sub-indeterminate part.

And, similarly, the determinate part of the 2-refined literal neutrosophic number $N_2 = b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2$ is b_0 , while b_1 is its first sub-indeterminate part, and b_2 is its second sub-indeterminate part.

$$\text{Denote } (a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2) \div (b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2) = \frac{a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2}{b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2} \equiv x + yI_1 + zI_2$$

where $a_0, a_1, a_2, b_0, b_1, b_2$ are known real numbers, while x, y, z are unknown real numbers we need to find out.

We know that

$$I_1 \cdot I_1 = I_1$$

$$I_2 \cdot I_2 = I_2$$

$$I_1 \cdot I_2 = I_2 \cdot I_1 = I_1$$

where I_1, I_2 are literal sub-indeterminacies.

By identification (\equiv) method, we have:

$$\frac{a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2}{b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2} \equiv x + yI_1 + zI_2$$

$$\text{or } a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 \equiv (b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2) \cdot (x + yI_1 + zI_2)$$

Whence:

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 &\equiv b_0x + b_0yI_1 + b_0zI_2 + b_1I_1x + b_1I_1yI_1 + b_1I_1zI_2 + b_2I_2x + b_2I_2yI_1 + b_2I_2zI_2 \\ &\equiv b_0x + b_0yI_1 + b_0zI_2 + b_1I_1x + b_1I_1y + b_1I_1z + b_2I_2x + b_2I_2y + b_2I_2z \\ &\equiv b_0x + (b_0y + b_1x + b_1y + b_1z)I_1 + (b_0z + b_2x + b_2z)I_2 \end{aligned}$$

We get a linear system of 3 equations with 3 variables x, y, z :

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_0 &= b_0x \\
 a_1 &= b_0y + b_1x + b_1y + b_1z = b_1x + (b_0 + b_1)y + b_1z \\
 a_2 &= b_0z + b_2x + b_2z = b_2x + (b_0 + b_2)z
 \end{aligned}$$

that we need to solve. It has no solution: if $b_0 = 0$ and $a_0 \neq 0$,

or if $b_0 + b_2 = 0$ and $a_0 + a_2 \neq 0$, or if $b_0 + b_1 + b_2 = 0$ and $a_0 + a_1 + a_2 \neq 0$.

2.8. Division of 2-Refined Literal Neutrosophic Numbers using the AH-Isometry

Let $R[I_1, I_2] = \{a + bI_1 + cI_2; a, b, c \in R\}$, where R is the set of real numbers, be the **2-Refined Literal Neutrosophic Numbers Ring**.

Let $f : R[I_1, I_2] \times R[I_1, I_2] \rightarrow R[I_1, I_2]$ be a 2-refined literal neutrosophic function (or operation) of two variables.

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 &f(a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2, b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2) = \\
 &= f(a_0, b_0) + [f(a_0 + a_1 + a_2, b_0 + b_1 + b_2) - f(a_0 + a_2, b_0 + b_2)]I_1 + [f(a_0 + a_2, b_0 + b_2) - f(a_0, b_0)]I_2 \\
 &= \frac{a_0}{b_0} + \left[\frac{a_0 + a_1 + a_2}{b_0 + b_1 + b_2} - \frac{a_0 + a_2}{b_0 + b_2} \right]I_1 + \left[\frac{a_0 + a_2}{b_0 + b_2} - \frac{a_0}{b_0} \right]I_2
 \end{aligned}$$

which works when all denominators $b_0, b_0 + b_2, b_0 + b_1 + b_2$ are different from zero.

If $b_0 = 0$ and $a_0 = 0$, or if $b_0 + b_2 = 0$ and $a_0 + a_2 = 0$, or if $b_0 + b_1 + b_2 = 0$ and $a_0 + a_1 + a_2 = 0$,

it may be possible to get some solutions, depending on each application.

Let $g : R[I_1, I_2] \rightarrow R[I_1, I_2]$ be a 2-refined literal neutrosophic function (or operation) of one variable. Using the AH-Isometry, we get:

$$g(a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2) = g(a_0) + [g(a_0 + a_1 + a_2) - g(a_0 + a_2)]I_1 + [g(a_0 + a_2) - g(a_0)]I_2 \quad (*)$$

3. Example of 2-Refined AH-Isometry:

Calculate the natural logarithm: $L = \ln(5 + 2I_1 - 3I_2)$.

We know about the argument $5 + 2I_1 - 3I_2$ that its determinate part is 5, its first sub-indeterminate part is $2I_1$, and his second sub-indeterminate part is $-3I_2$.

But we do not know the determinate part, nor the first and second sub-indeterminate parts, of the whole expression L . The AH-Isometry helps us to find them.

The function $g = \ln$ (natural logarithm), $a_0 = 5$, $a_1 = 2$, $a_2 = -3$ and we substitute them into the above (*) relationship.

$$\begin{aligned} L &= \ln(5) + [\ln(5+2+(-3)) - \ln(5+(-3))] I_1 + [\ln(5+(-3)) - \ln(5)] I_2 \\ &= \ln(5) + [\ln(4) - \ln(2)] I_1 + [\ln(2) - \ln(5)] I_2 \\ &= \ln(5) + \ln(4/2) \cdot I_1 + \ln(2/5) \cdot I_2 \\ &= \ln(5) + \ln(2) \cdot I_1 + \ln(0.4) \cdot I_2 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the determinate part of L is $\ln(5)$, the first sub-indeterminate part of L is $\ln(2)$, and the second sub-indeterminate part of L is $\ln(0.4)$.

4. Examples of 2-Refined Numerical Neutrosophic Numbers

First Example:

$$N_1 = 5 + 4I_1 - 2I_2 = 5 + 4 \cdot (0.\overline{35}) - 2 \cdot (0.\overline{127})$$

where the determinate part of N_1 is 5, while the numerical sub-indeterminacies parts are:

$$I_1 = 0.\overline{35} = 0.353535 \dots \text{ (infinitely many decimals),}$$

$$I_2 = 0.\overline{127} = 0.127127127 \dots \text{ (infinitely many decimals).}$$

Second Example:

$$N_2 = -2 + e + 3\pi = -2 + 1 \cdot I_1 - 3I_2, \text{ where}$$

$$I_1 = e = 2.7182818 \dots \text{ and}$$

$$I_2 = \pi = 3.1415926 \dots$$

5. Example of 4-Refined Numerical Neutrosophic Numbers:

$$\begin{aligned} N_4 &= 8 + 2^2\sqrt[2]{7} - 6^3\sqrt[3]{111} + \sqrt[4]{54} - \sqrt[5]{4} \\ &\equiv 8 + 2I_1 - 6I_2 + I_3 - I_4 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$I_1 = \sqrt[2]{7} = 2.645751 \dots$$

$$I_2 = \sqrt[3]{111} = 4.805895 \dots$$

$$I_3 = \sqrt[4]{54} = 2.710806 \dots$$

$$I_4 = \sqrt[5]{4} = 1.319507 \dots$$

6. More Examples

Zeina and Abobala [4] have defined the literal neutrosophic ring:

$$R[I] = \{a + bI; a, b \in R\}, \text{ where } I = \text{literal indeterminacy, with } I^2 = I, \text{ where } a \text{ is the determinate}$$

part of the neutrosophic number $a + bI$, while bI is its indeterminate part.

A function, $f : R[I] \rightarrow R[I]$, by using the AH-Isometry, can be calculated as:

$$f(a + bI) = f(a) + [f(a + b) - f(a)]I$$

For example, $\sin(\frac{\pi}{3} + 0.5I) = \sin(\frac{\pi}{3}) + [\sin(\frac{\pi}{3} + 0.5) - \sin(\frac{\pi}{3})]I$, where the determinate part is $\sin(\frac{\pi}{3})$ and indeterminate part is $[\sin(\frac{\pi}{3} + 0.5) - \sin(\frac{\pi}{3})]I$.

Into the original expression $\sin(\frac{\pi}{3} + 0.5I)$ it is not clear what is the determinate part and what is the indeterminate part. The AH-Isometry helped us distinguish between these parts.

7. Theorem of Isomorphism:

Let $R_n(I) = \{a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n a_i I_i; a_i \in R\}$ be the n-refined neutrosophic real ring.

Define:

$$f: R_n(I) \rightarrow R \times R \times \dots \times R \quad (n + 1 \text{ times})$$

$$f(a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n a_i I_i) = (a_0, \sum_{i=0}^n a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1}^n a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2}^n a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2,3}^n a_i, \dots, a_0 + a_n)$$

Then f is a ring isomorphism.

Proof:

It is clear that f is well-defined mapping and preserves addition operation. We must prove that it keeps multiplication.

Assume that $A = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n a_i I_i$, $B = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n b_i I_i$, then for $n = 2$, according to the refined AH-isometry the theorem holds see [3]. Assume that it is true for k , we prove for $k+1$.

Assume that $A = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{k+1} a_i I_i$, $B = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{k+1} b_i I_i$

$$A \cdot B = (a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k a_i I_i + a_{k+1} I_{k+1})(b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i I_i + b_{k+1} I_{k+1}) = (a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k a_i I_i)(b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i I_i) + (a_{k+1} I_{k+1})(b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i I_i) + (a_{k+1} I_{k+1})(b_{k+1} I_{k+1}) + (a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k a_i I_i)(b_{k+1} I_{k+1}) =$$

$$(a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k a_i I_i)(b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i I_i) + a_{k+1} b_0 I_{k+1} + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i a_{k+1} I_i + a_{k+1} b_{k+1} I_{k+1} + (a_0 b_{k+1} I_{k+1} + \sum_{i=1}^k b_{k+1} a_i I_i) = (a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k a_i I_i)(b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i I_i) + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i a_{k+1} I_i + (a_{k+1} b_0 + a_{k+1} b_{k+1} + a_0 b_{k+1}) I_{k+1} + \sum_{i=1}^k a_i b_{k+1} I_i,$$

put $T = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k a_i I_i$, $S = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i I_i$, then

$$A \cdot B = TS + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i a_{k+1} I_i + (a_{k+1} b_0 + a_{k+1} b_{k+1} + a_0 b_{k+1}) I_{k+1} + \sum_{i=1}^k a_i b_{k+1} I_i.$$

On the other hand, we have:

$$f(A \cdot B) = f(TS) + f(\sum_{i=1}^k b_i a_{k+1} I_i) + f((a_{k+1} b_0 + a_{k+1} b_{k+1} + a_0 b_{k+1}) I_{k+1}) + f(\sum_{i=1}^k a_i b_{k+1} I_i) =$$

$$= f(T)f(S) + (0, \sum_{i=1}^k b_i a_{k+1}, \sum_{i \neq 1}^n b_i a_{k+1}, \dots, b_k a_{k+1}) + (0, a_{k+1} b_0 + a_{k+1} b_{k+1} +$$

$$a_0 b_{k+1}, a_{k+1} b_0 + a_{k+1} b_{k+1} + a_0 b_{k+1}, \dots, a_{k+1} b_0 + a_{k+1} b_{k+1} + a_0 b_{k+1}) +$$

$$(0, \sum_{i=1}^k a_i b_{k+1}, \sum_{i \neq 1}^k a_i b_{k+1}, \dots, a_k b_{k+1}) =$$

$$\left(a_0, \sum_{i=0}^k a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1}^k a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2}^k a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2,3}^k a_i, \dots, a_0 + a_k \right) \cdot (b_0, \sum_{i=0}^k b_i, \sum_{i \neq 1}^k b_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2}^k b_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2,3}^k b_i, \dots, b_0$$

$$+ b_k) +$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (0, a_{k+1}, \dots, a_{k+1}) \cdot (0, \sum_{i=1}^k b_i, \sum_{i \neq 0,1}^k b_i, \sum_{i \neq 0,1,2}^k b_i, \sum_{i \neq 0,1,2,3}^k b_i, \dots, b_k) + (0, a_{k+1}b_0 + \\
 & a_{k+1}b_{k+1} + a_0b_{k+1}, a_{k+1}b_0 + a_{k+1}b_{k+1} + a_0b_{k+1}, \dots, a_{k+1}b_0 + a_{k+1}b_{k+1} + a_0b_{k+1}) + \\
 & (0, b_{k+1}, \dots, b_{k+1}) \cdot (0, \sum_{i=1}^k a_i, \sum_{i \neq 0,1}^k a_i, \sum_{i \neq 0,1,2}^k a_i, \sum_{i \neq 0,1,2,3}^k a_i, \dots, a_k) = \\
 & \left(a_0, \sum_{i=0}^k a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1}^k a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2}^k a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2,3}^k a_i, \dots, a_0 + a_k \right) \cdot (b_0, \sum_{i=0}^k b_i, \sum_{i \neq 1}^k b_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2}^k b_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2,3}^k b_i, \dots, b_0 \\
 & + b_k) + \\
 & (0, a_{k+1}, \dots, a_{k+1}) \cdot (0, \sum_{i=1}^k b_i + b_0 + b_{k+1}, \sum_{i \neq 0,1}^k b_i + b_0 + b_{k+1}, \sum_{i \neq 0,1,2}^k b_i + b_0 + \\
 & b_{k+1}, \dots, b_0 + b_k + b_{k+1}) + (0, a_0, \dots, a_0) \cdot (0, b_{k+1}, \dots, b_{k+1}) = \\
 & (a_0, \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1}^{k+1} a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2}^{k+1} a_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2,3}^{k+1} a_i, \dots, a_0 + a_k) \cdot \\
 & (b_0, \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} b_i, \sum_{i \neq 1}^{k+1} b_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2}^{k+1} b_i, \sum_{i \neq 1,2,3}^{k+1} b_i, \dots, b_0 + b_k) = f(A) \cdot f(B).
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, f is a ring isomorphism, and it is called the **n -Refined Neutrosophic AH-Isometry**.

8. Examples of 3- and 4-Refined Neutrosophic Isomorphisms

For $n = 3$, the 3-refined neutrosophic case, the formula of f is

$$f(a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 + a_3I_3) = (a_0, a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3, a_0 + a_2 + a_3, a_0 + a_3).$$

For $n = 4$, the 4-refined neutrosophic case, the formula of f is

$$\begin{aligned}
 & f(a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 + a_3I_3 + a_4I_4) \\
 & = (a_0, a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3 + a_4, a_0 + a_2 + a_3 + a_4, a_0 + a_3 + a_4, a_0 + a_4).
 \end{aligned}$$

9. Inverse AH-Isomorphism

The formula of inverse isomorphism is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & f^{-1}: R \times R \times \dots \times R \text{ (} n + 1 \text{ times)} \rightarrow R_n(I) \text{ such that:} \\
 & f^{-1}(a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3 \dots a_n) = a_0 + I_1(a_1 - a_2) + I_2(a_2 - a_3) + I_3(a_3 - a_4) + \dots + I_n(a_n - a_0).
 \end{aligned}$$

Application:

Find the inverse of the following 3-refined neutrosophic real number $x = 1 + I_1 + I_2 + I_3$.

Now, we will see how the n -refined AH-isometry is very powerful in simplifying hard computations.

First, we compute: $f(x) = (1, 4, 3, 2)$, $[f(x)]^{-1} = (1, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2})$, hence:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x^{-1} &= f^{-1}[[f(x)]^{-1}] = 1 + \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{3}\right)I_1 + \left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{2}\right)I_2 + \left(\frac{1}{2} - 1\right)I_3 = 1 + \left(-\frac{1}{12}\right)I_1 + \left(-\frac{1}{6}\right)I_2 + \\
 & \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)I_3.
 \end{aligned}$$

By an easy computation, we can see:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x \cdot x^{-1} &= 1 + \left(-\frac{1}{12} - \frac{1}{12} - \frac{1}{12} - \frac{1}{12} - \frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{2} + 1\right)I_1 + \left(-\frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{2} + 1\right)I_2 + \left(-\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} + \right. \\
 & \left. 1\right)I_3 = 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

10. Conclusion

We extended for the first time the Neutrosophic AH-Isometry to n-Refined Neutrosophic AH-Isometry, to find the determinate part of a function, as well as its multiple sub-indeterminate parts.

Many real examples of n-refined neutrosophic numbers, that have a determinate part and many types of sub-indeterminacies, were presented.

The AH-Isometry is designed to find the determinate part and sub-indeterminate parts of a n-refined neutrosophic function of the form $f(a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 + \dots + a_nI_n)$.

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